

QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATION OF FATIGUE MICROCRACK GROWTH

IN SiC WHISKER REINFORCED 2124 Al ALLOY COMPOSITES

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Summary

Extrinsic sources of fatigue crack initiation in silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum alloy composites include unbonded SiC particles, which usually occur when clusters of SiC are present, and non-SiC intermetallics, which are often cracked during prior mechanical deformation processing. The bonded interface between SiC and the 2124 Al alloy matrix is an intrinsic defect; however, reducing clustering of SiC and the number and size of non-SiC intermetallics increased fatigue life by more than tenfold. Crack propagation is more rapid along SiC-Al interfaces than through the matrix and link-up of cracks along the SiC-Al interface has been observed, contributing to final failure. Failure at nominal stresses of 300 and 350 MPa is very rapid beyond an observed crack length of 30 microns.

The 2124 Al alloy without SiC has a much shorter fatigue life at the same applied stress due to its much lower cyclic yield stress (320 MPa vs. 580 for the SiC/Al), but supports cracks up to 500 microns long without rapid failure at a nominal stress of 300 MPa.

Introduction

While 2124 Al alloy matrix SiC composites have higher strength and stiffness than the alloys without reinforcement with little added density (1-6), as shown in Table I, their fatigue properties are not well understood, at least based on the dearth of information in the open literature (reference (7) appears to be the only publication to date). The purpose of the present research is to characterize the fatigue crack initiation and microcrack growth behavior of silicon carbide whisker reinforced 2124 aluminum alloy, with particular attention to the role of microstructure.

Materials and Specimens

The materials used in this research were manufactured by ARCO Metals Company Silag Operation, with four heats being studied: 25 vol. pct. SiC whisker in Al 6061-T6 (supplied by Dr. C. R. Crowe of the Naval Surface Weapons Center (7), October, 1982, no Heat # given); Heat #A6104Z-2A, 20 vol. pct. SiC whisker in Al 2124-T4 (received from Silag June, 1983); Heat #A2038Z-C, 20 vol. pct. SiC whisker in Al 2124-T6 (received from Silag November, 1983); Heat #A8050W, Al 2124-F (received from Silag November, 1983; heat treated to T6 after receipt). The two batches of SiC whisker/Al-2124 reflect changes in proprietary processing variables as well as the different heat treatments; the Al 2124 alloy was made to serve as a baseline reference on powder metallurgy Al using the same processing as the SiC whisker reinforced Al 2124 alloy.

The specimen geometries used for this work are shown in Fig. 1. Figure 1A shows the crack initiation/growth specimen design. This configuration was selected to provide a well-defined crack initiation region. The stress concentration factor for the notch was determined from specimen dimensions using a graph by Peterson (8), and was typically in the range 1.2-1.4. Figure 1B

Figure 1 - A: Crack initiation/growth specimen configuration showing load vector and location for taking replicas; B: Dogbone specimen for elastic modulus and cyclic yield strength determination; C: Specimen for in situ fracture in scanning Auger microprobe. All dimensions in mm.

Table I. Cyclic Yield Strengths and Elastic Moduli for Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C and Al 2124-T6, Heat #A8050W, Compared with Values from the Literature (1-6)

Made By	Volume Percent Whisker	Alloy-Temper	Young's Modulus GPa	Yield Strength MPa	Tension/Compression/Unloading	Monotonic/Cyclic/Ultrasonic	Transverse/Longitudinal	Reference
Silag	25	2024-T42	110	365	T	M	L	1
unknown	32	2024-?	131	---	-	U	L	2
unknown	32	2024-?	116	---	-	U	T	2
Silag	15	2024-T4	89-97	---	T	M	L	3
Silag	20	2024-T4	97-117	---	T	M	L	3
Silag	20	2024-T4	97-117	448-482	C	M	L	3
Silag	25	2024-T4	117-151	---	T	M	L	3
Silag	25	2024-T4	124-152	641-690	C	M	L	3
unknown	20	2024-T4	96.3	386	T	M	L	4
unknown	20	2024-T4	93.7	419	T	M	T	4
unknown	13	2024-T4	96	398	U	M	L	5
unknown	13	2024-T6	97	436	U	M	L	5
Silag	20	2024-T6	---	498	C	M	L	6
Silag	20	2124-T6	128	560	T	C	L	this work
Silag	20	2124-T6	128	600	C	C	L	this work
Silag	0	2124-T6	76	310	T	C	L	this work
Silag	0	2124-T6	76	330	C	C	L	this work

shows the dogbone specimen used for elastic modulus and yield strength tests. Figure 1C shows the specimen design used for in situ fracture studies of interfaces in the scanning Auger microprobe.

Preparation of all types of specimens began with the cutting of rectangular blanks from the plate material furnished using a band saw. Rectangular blanks for crack initiation (Fig. 1A) and elastic modulus/cyclic yield strength (Fig. 1B) were then squared up using a carbide end mill.

Crack initiation specimens (Fig. 1A) were notched using a carbide tool bit in a fly cutter set to 25.4 mm radius. Machined specimens were then polished to 600 grit finish using SiC abrasive paper. Notches were polished by wrapping the abrasive paper around an Al mandrel 50.8 mm in diameter and holding the specimen against the mandrel as it turned in a drill press. Flat surfaces were polished on metallographic polishing wheels. Final polishing was done by hand using diamond polishing compound on Buehler Texmet (trademark) polishing cloth. Both flat surfaces and notches were polished using 9 micron diamond compound until scratches from previous polishing were removed. Notches were then final-polished with 1 micron diamond compound until scratches were reduced to only a few parallel to the stress axis.

Reduced cross sections in specimens for elastic modulus and cyclic yield strength tests (Fig. 1B) were machined into the rectangular blanks using a 12.7 mm (0.5 in.) diameter carbide end mill. The specimens were then ground to 600 grit finish using SiC paper to remove machining marks.

Specimens for use in the scanning Auger microprobe (Fig. 1C) were made by turning the rectangular blanks in a lathe to the desired diameter, and then the notch was turned. As these specimens were for examination of fracture surfaces, no polishing was needed.

Experimental Procedures

Fatigue Crack Initiation and Microcrack Growth

Fatigue crack initiation and microcrack growth experiments were conducted using an MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine. Specimens were loaded axially using a fully reversed ($R=-1$) inverted sine waveform under load control, as shown in Fig. 2. Surface replicas were taken at the base of the notch using Bioden replicating film softened in acetone at several times during the experiment with the specimen held under maximum tensile load (points "a" and "e" in Fig. 2) to ensure that any cracks present would be

Figure 2 - Fatigue loading waveform for crack initiation and microcrack growth tests and microcrack closure tests. Replicas for initiation-and-growth tests were taken at the tensile peak. Replicas for closure tests were taken at successive points "a" through "e".

open and thus more visible. This procedure has been used elsewhere (9-11). Experiments on the SiC/Al alloy composite were run to final fracture, which was very rapid after reaching an observed crack length of 30 microns with nominal applied stresses of 300 and 350 MPa. Experiments on unreinforced Al were terminated when a macroscopic crack was observed visually.

Microcrack Closure

Microcrack closure experiments followed the pattern of the fatigue crack initiation and microcrack growth tests except that the specimen was marked with a surface scratch to facilitate location of the same area in all the replicas. The specimen was held at several points during a single loading cycle, as shown in Fig. 2. Replicas were taken at each point to trace the evolution of crack opening displacement.

Elastic Modulus and Cyclic Yield Strength

Elastic modulus and cyclic yield strength of the newer composite (Heat #A2038Z-C) and the unreinforced Al alloy were measured using dogbone specimens (Fig. 1B) under axial strain control with an inverted ramp waveform. An MTS extensometer of 7.62 mm (0.3 in.) gage length was used to measure strain. Hysteresis loops were recorded using an x-y recorder after 100 cycles at each of several strain amplitudes in the range 0.1% to 1%.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Replicas were selected from each fatigue experiment to study the initiation and growth of microcracks through the course of the experiment. These replicas were vacuum coated with aluminum, then shadowed with gold or gold-palladium for contrast. This single-stage technique yields replicas which are negative casts of the original surfaces so that depressed areas on the actual specimens appear raised on the replicas and cracks appear white instead of black.

Scanning electron microscopy was done using a JEOL JSM-50A (at Northwestern University) or a JEOL JSM-35CF (at ARCO Metals Technical Center), beginning with the highest-cycle replica to locate and photograph cracks late in the test. By noting the coordinates of each crack and taking low magnification locator pictures, it was possible to find the same cracks in other replicas at lower cycle counts. This allows measurement of individual crack growth rates as well as the accumulation of enough measurements for statistical analysis.

Transmission Electron Microscopy

Thin foils were made from as-received and fatigued samples of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, by cutting a thin slice using a slow-speed saw and then grinding to approximately 0.1 mm thickness on SiC paper. Discs 3 mm in diameter were cut from the foil using an electric discharge machine and then jet polished using a solution of 80% CH₃OH and 20% HNO₃ in methanol at -70°C and 95 mA. The foils were examined in a Hitachi H-700H operated at 175 kV. The use of a double-tilt stage allowed the specimen to be oriented to show dislocations clearly.

Auger Electron Spectroscopy

Auger electron spectroscopy was performed on fracture surfaces of specimens of Silag SiC (25 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (6061-T6) fractured in the ultra-high-vacuum chamber of a Physical Electronics Model 590A scanning Auger microprobe. Fracture surfaces were examined immediately after the specimen had been fractured and moved under the electron beam. The incident electron beam was too large in diameter to probe a SiC whisker without also picking up some of the surrounding matrix, so Auger electron spectra were taken with the beam centered on a SiC whisker to get a SiC-rich region and then with the beam centered on the matrix to get an Al-rich region.

Experimental Results

Microcrack Closure

The effect of crack closure on fatigue crack propagation has been extensively studied (12-21) since the first report on the phenomenon by Elber (14). The use of crack closure load to define an effective stress intensity range has been shown to reconcile apparent discrepancies in the relationship between fatigue crack growth rate and stress intensity range (13), including the effects of fracture surface oxidation (15), residual stress relaxation (18), and surface roughness (15,17). The case of short cracks is further complicated by the interaction of the crack with grain boundaries and intermetallic particles (16) as well as the change from mixed mode (I and II) propagation for short cracks to pure mode I propagation for long cracks (20). Grain boundaries act as barriers to slip band propagation thus limiting the plastic zone for short cracks to the distance from the crack tip to the grain boundary (18), which may nonetheless give a large plastic zone size relative to the crack length (16). Particles should also play a role in limiting slip distances. Threshold stress intensity ranges for short cracks can fall below those for long cracks (19,21), with a value of $0.15 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$ reported for Al 2219-T851 (19).

Figure 3A shows the apparent crack opening width (based on shadow tail length) normalized to the width at the tensile peak at the start of the series of replicas for several cracks for Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C. Some cracks appear to close completely as the load is reduced, while others remain open throughout the cycle. Longer cracks close at some points along their length, but also show some open areas. Figure 3B shows crack opening displacement at zero load divided by crack length as a function of crack length. The trend of decreasing crack opening width with increasing crack length is opposite to that observed by Morris (17) in 2219-T851 Al alloy, but seems to agree with results obtained by Asaro et al. (12) for 2048 Al alloy, who found a transition to a lower crack closure load as the calculated plastic zone size reached the grain size. The effect in the case of the SiC/Al alloy composite appears to correlate with the spacing of the SiC whiskers, with wider crack opening at zero load for cracks less than approximately 1.5 microns long and much smaller crack opening at zero load for longer cracks.

Elastic Modulus and Cyclic Yield Strength

Table I gives Young's moduli and monotonic yield strengths for SiC whisker reinforced 2024 Al alloy with whisker volume fractions ranging from 13 to 32 percent. There is some indication of an effect of orientation on both modulus and yield strength (2,4). The modulus is higher in the

Figure 3 - A: Normalized apparent crack opening width versus applied load from tensile peak to tensile peak for Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C; B: Apparent crack opening width at zero load divided by crack length versus crack length for the same specimen.

longitudinal direction than in the transverse direction, no doubt due to whisker alignment resulting from deformation processing of the material. The one case in which longitudinal and transverse yield strengths are given shows the opposite effect: higher transverse yield strength than longitudinal. The higher yield stress for the transverse case may be due to the fact that fracture of SiC seems necessary for transverse fracture while at least some pull-out of SiC whiskers occurs for the longitudinal case. Another factor may be that for the transverse case the stress concentration effect is distributed along the length of the whiskers while for the longitudinal case the stress concentration is confined to the whisker ends. Publication dates for the references (1-6) range from 1980 to 1984 so the data are for older material than used in the present work. This vintage factor helps to account for the higher modulus obtained for the Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6) (Heat #A2038Z-C) in the present work when compared with the data from the literature. The problem of comparing cyclic and monotonic yield strengths is more difficult since there is some indication that Al alloy 2024 can cyclically harden if tested in the naturally aged (T4) condition, but cyclically softens if tested in the artificially aged (T6) condition (22). Cyclic hardening is usually associated with increasing dislocation density while cyclic softening results from the elimination of obstacles to dislocation motion, such as shearing of intermetallic particles by dislocations (23). Since the SiC can't be sheared by dislocations in the Al alloy matrix, SiC/Al alloy composites should cyclically harden due to increasing dislocation density in the matrix. Direct experimental evidence for the present material has not yet been obtained; however, indirect evidence in the form of increased dislocation density due to fatigue appears in the section on transmission electron microscopy below.

A simple approach to estimating the Young's modulus of a composite material is to use a rule of mixtures. Taking moduli $M_1 = 470$ GPa for SiC whiskers (24) and $M_2 = 76$ GPa for 2124-T6 Al alloy (this work), estimates of the modulus, M , of the $v = 20$ vol. pct. SiC whisker reinforced Al 2124-T6 alloy can be obtained using either the Voigt or Reuss equations, as shown in Equations (1) and (2):

$$\text{Voigt: } M = vM_1 + (1-v)M_2 \quad (1a)$$

$$M = 0.2*470 + (1-0.2)*76 = 155 \text{ GPa} \quad (1b)$$

$$\text{Reuss: } M = \frac{1}{v/M_1 + (1-v)/M_2} \quad (2a)$$

$$M = \frac{1}{0.2/470 + (1-0.2)/76} \quad (2b)$$

The measured value in Table I of 128 GPa is between the two estimates. Previously it was suggested that deviation from the linear law of mixtures (Voigt averaging) indicates poor load transfer across the interface between phases (25). The low values of Young's modulus reported in the literature for SiC/Al alloy may be due to poor bonding.

Figure 4 shows the cyclic stress-strain curves for Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6) (Heat #A2038Z-C) (Fig. 4A) and the unreinforced Al 2124-T6 alloy (Heat #A8050W) (Fig. 4B). These curves were obtained by taking the tips of the hysteresis loops ($\epsilon_{\max}, \sigma_{\max}$), ($\epsilon_{\min}, \sigma_{\min}$) and plotting them on stress-strain axes. A smooth curve was fitted to the data by eye, and the 0.2% offset yield strength was determined by constructing lines parallel to the elastic portion of the curve but offset by 0.2%.

Figure 4 - A: Cyclic stress-strain curve for Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C; B: Cyclic stress-strain curve for Al 2124-T6, Heat #A8050W.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

Figure 5 is a representative scanning electron micrograph of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4) which has not been fatigued. The non-SiC intermetallic particles are readily identified by their larger, more nearly equiaxed morphology and lighter color from the long, narrow and dark SiC whiskers. Energy dispersive x-ray analysis of the non-SiC intermetallics identified them as $(Fe,Mn)Al_5$.

Figure 6 is a representative series of scanning electron micrographs of single-stage surface replicas of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, fatigued under a stress amplitude of 350 MPa and load ratio of -1. The cracks have initiated at the poles of SiC whiskers and propagated into the matrix. Examination of replicas taken at the first tensile peak show no cracks, so initiation occurs due to fatigue and not monotonic stress at this stress. Where the SiC-Al alloy interfaces run nearly parallel to the crack propagation direction, the crack tends to run along the interfaces. The crack does not generally follow an unfavorably oriented interface.

Figures 7 to 9 are representative scanning electron micrographs of single-stage replicas of the Al 2124-T6 alloy (Heat #A8050W) fatigued under a stress amplitude of 300 MPa and load ratio of -1. Figure 7 shows cracks initiating along slip bands emanating from a small intermetallic particle.

Figure 5 - Scanning electron micrograph of non-fatigued specimen of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4), Heat #A6104Z-2A. Features marked A are non-SiC intermetallics; B denotes clumps of SiC.

Figure 8 also shows slip-band cracking, some of which is apparently not associated with any intermetallic particles. Figure 9 shows cracks developing along what appears to be a grain boundary by a cavitation mechanism.

Examination of several hundred such pictures revealed that the earlier Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4), Heat #A6104Z-2A, has a significant number of clumps of SiC without intervening matrix, which clumps can act as micro-voids in the material, as well as many non-SiC intermetallics of sizes on the order of a few tens of microns. The non-SiC intermetallics are often cracked prior to fatigue, apparently as a result of the deformation processing performed on the material; some of these pre-cracks are propagated during the fatigue experiment. The newer Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, shows very few clumps of SiC, and fewer and smaller non-SiC intermetallics. The unreinforced Al 2124-T6 alloy, Heat #A8050W, showed two types of intermetallics in the as-received (as-rolled) condition: one Cu-bearing, probably S-phase, the other $(\text{Fe,Mn})\text{Al}_3$. The replicas of heat treated (T6) and fatigued specimens show substantially fewer intermetallics, suggesting that the Cu-bearing phase was dissolved in the solution treatment and did not regain its former size during aging.

Transmission Electron Microscopy

Figures 10 and 11 are representative transmission electron micrographs of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, without fatigue and after 2960 cycles at 350 MPa. The dislocation distribution in the non-fatigued specimen is highly non-uniform within what appears to be a single grain, with dislocations piled up alongside one side of a whisker but not the other. The fatigued specimen shows a more uniform distribution of dislocations.

Figure 6 - Scanning electron micrographs of replicas of a specimen of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, showing the crack evolution from 800 to 2000 to 5000 cycles at 350 MPa stress amplitude. Cracks are labeled A through E. Note that cracks initiate at the interface between the SiC and Al alloy and propagate along favorably oriented SiC-Al alloy interfaces. At 5000 cycles, cracks A and B have linked up and cracks C and D are about to follow suit.

Figure 7 - Scanning electron micrographs of replicas of a specimen of Al (2124-T6), Heat #A8050, showing crack evolution from 100 to 500 to 1500 cycles at 300 MPa. Cracking is along slip bands emanating from an inter-metallic particle.

Figure 8 - Scanning electron micrographs of replicas of a specimen of Al (2124-T6), Heat #A8050, showing crack evolution from 100 to 500 to 1500 cycles at 300 MPa. Cracking is along slip bands, some not associated with intermetallic particles.

Figure 9 - Scanning electron micrographs of replicas of a specimen of Al (2124-T6), Heat #A8050, showing crack evolution from 100 to 500 to 1500 cycles at 300 MPa. Cracking is along a grain boundary.

Figure 10 - Transmission electron micrograph bright field and dark field pair from a non-fatigued foil of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C. Note the non-uniform dislocation distribution.

Figure 11 - Transmission electron micrograph bright field and dark field pair from a foil from a fatigued (2960 cycles at 350 MPa, R = -1) specimen of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C. Note the more uniform dislocation distribution as compared with Fig. 12.

Interface

Several studies of SiC-coated boron fiber reinforced Al composites, SiC whisker or particle reinforced Al, and sintered SiC-molten Al have been published (26-33). Arsenault and Pande (26) examined Silag SiC whisker reinforced Al (alloy not specified) using scanning transmission electron microscopy and in situ fracture in a scanning Auger microprobe and reported that Al had apparently diffused into the SiC to a depth of approximately 0.2 microns. Iseki et al. (27) found Al_4C_3 by transmission electron microscopy at interfaces formed by dipping pressureless sintered SiC into molten Al; but no Al_4C_3 was found at the interface between reaction sintered SiC dipped into molten Al. Marcus (28) found little SiC on in situ fracture surfaces of Silag SiC (22.45 wt. pct. whisker)/Al (2024) examined in a scanning Auger microprobe, but found small bits of $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ at a few interfaces during transmission electron microscopy of thin foils. Marcus (28) then heated samples to 550°C for 24 hours but still found no evidence of reaction between the SiC and Al during transmission electron microscopy of thin foils. Nieh and Karlak (29) inferred "good wetting" of SiC by liquid Al as an explanation for good shape retention of a block of SiC whisker/Al (6061) heated to 1000°C for 1 hour. They also reported that SiC in contact with molten Al is "chemically stable at temperatures well above the melting point of the metal" (29). Prewo and Kreider (30) found no evidence of reaction between Al (6061) and the SiC coating on boron fibers examined by transmission electron microscopy, but reported intimate contact at both the boron-SiC and SiC-Al interfaces. Prewo and McCarthy (31) stated that "the SiC coating inhibits the reaction between the [boron] fiber and [Al] matrix", and stated that there was "no evidence ... that a chemical reaction took place" at either the B-SiC or SiC-Al interface, based on transmission electron microscopy. Skinner et al. (32,33) reported no interfacial reaction in DWA SiC particulate/Al (2124), apparently based on SEM.

The primary source of fatigue crack initiation in SiC/Al composites is debonding at the SiC-Al interface. An attempt was made at examining the interface by fracturing specimens of Silag SiC (25 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (6061-T6) inside the ultrahigh vacuum chamber of a Physical Electronics Model 590A scanning Auger microprobe. The electron beam size was too large to illuminate only a SiC whisker, so the results obtained only reflect areas higher or lower in SiC, as previously reported by Marcus (28). There appeared to be an oxide on the surface of the SiC, though its exact composition was not determined. This is suggested to be the $\gamma-Al_2O_3$ reported by Marcus (28). This observation would seem to correlate with the apparent brittle nature of the interface as deduced from the fatigue experiments.

Figure 12A shows what appears to be a small adherend on an otherwise denuded whisker observed in the transmission electron microscope. Figure 12B shows a whisker with an uneven surface, possibly due to very small adherends. Diffraction patterns were not obtained in this survey so the adherends cannot be identified. They may be $\gamma-Al_2O_3$, as observed by Marcus (28).

Analysis

Micromechanical Models for Fatigue Crack Initiation

Much effort has been devoted to the study of fatigue crack initiation in engineering alloys (9,34-51). Three major categories of fatigue crack initiation have been found: (a) along slip bands within grains (34-41); (b) along grain boundaries (9,36,37); and (c) from inclusions (9,36,38,42-51). Micromechanical and statistical models have been proposed to describe these

Figure 12 - Transmission electron micrographs of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, (fatigued 2960 cycles at 350 MPa, R=-1). A: Note the adherend on the otherwise denuded whisker, which is protruding into the hole made by the jet polisher. B: Note the uneven surface of the whisker marked by the arrow.

fatigue crack initiation mechanisms in terms of dislocations and obstacles to their motion such as grain boundaries and inclusions (52-56).

The primary source of fatigue crack initiation in SiC whisker reinforced 2124 Al alloys in the absence of extrinsic defects is the apparent debonding of SiC whiskers from the Al matrix at the poles of the whiskers (see Fig. 6). The SiC is in this case behaving as an inclusion, not unlike the intermetallics and other impurities identified as fatigue crack initiators by several other investigators (36,38,42-51). Some intermetallics are weak enough for the crack to pass through them, such as the phases observed in Al 2024 by Kung and Fine (38) and Al 2219 by Morris (49). Other intermetallics resist cracking but have weak interfaces which serve as crack paths around the particles.

Tanaka and Mura have proposed a dislocation dipole, "Theory of Fatigue Crack Initiation at Inclusions", (53), as an extension of their earlier theory for slip band cracking (52). This inclusion initiation model considers three types of fatigue crack initiation: (a) the inclusion debonds from the matrix on the first application of stress and thereafter behaves as a void or notch initiating a crack at its equator (see Fig. 13); (b) the inclusion remains bonded to the matrix at first but the dislocation pile-up in the matrix eventually causes the inclusion to crack or debond; (c) the inclusion neither cracks nor debonds but the matrix cracks along a slip band at one of the poles of the inclusion where the local stress is highest.

Figure 13 - Tanaka-Mura model for fatigue crack initiation from inclusions. A: Inclusion debonds on first application of load. B: Inclusion cracks due to dislocation pile-up in matrix. C: Inclusion remains bonded; crack initiates on slip bands developed at pole of inclusion which is where the stress concentration is highest (53).

A statistical model for fatigue crack initiation from inclusions has been proposed by Morris and co-workers (54-56). This model takes into account the inclusion width normal to the stress axis, the maximum slip distance within the grain measured at 45° to the stress axis (which will be the direction of maximum resolved shear stress, the driving force for dislocation motion), the applied stress, and material constants. This model is used with a Monte Carlo computer simulation to mimic experimental data and generally agrees with the experimental observation that crack initiation probability increases as the size of the inclusion (stress concentration factor) and the maximum slip distance (ease of deformation) increase.

The models of fatigue crack initiation due to intermetallic particles don't fully explain the results obtained in the present work on SiC whisker reinforced Al. The Tanaka-Mura model considers a single inclusion in an apparently infinite solid; the Morris model considers a single inclusion in a relatively large grain of matrix material. The SiC/Al-alloy composites have a very high density of SiC whiskers and consequently a very short mean

free path through the matrix which severely restricts dislocation motion. A successful fatigue crack initiation model for SiC whisker reinforced Al alloys would have to account for the influence of the closely spaced SiC whiskers on the local stress distribution in the matrix, the accumulation of dislocations near the poles of the whiskers, the evolution from a dislocation pile-up to a crack, and the apparently random distribution of such occurrences. The model should also explain the preference of microcracks to propagate along favorably oriented whisker-matrix interfaces.

The transmission electron micrographs presented earlier in this paper may provide an explanation for the apparent randomness of the fatigue crack initiation process. The un-fatigued foil shows a highly non-uniform dislocation distribution, even within single grains. It may be that a high initial dislocation density near the pole of a whisker promotes fatigue crack initiation and the variation in dislocation density explains the observation that only a few percent of whiskers initiate cracks.

Statistics of Fatigue Microcrack Propagation

The density of cracks in the composite material is on the order of 10^6 per square meter after a few hundred fatigue cycles, based on the number of cracks observed in the area scanned. This high density suggests the use of a statistical treatment to characterize the data obtained in the crack initiation and growth experiments. Weibull statistics have become common for representing failure test data (57-59) and are used here. The Weibull cumulative distribution function is:

$$F(L) = 1 - \exp(-(L/\beta)^\alpha) . \quad (3)$$

The Weibull probability density function is:

$$\frac{dF(L)}{dL} = f(L) = \frac{\alpha L^{\alpha-1}}{\beta^\alpha} \exp(-(L/\beta)^\alpha) \quad (4)$$

where L is the variable; α is the shape parameter, which determines the sharpness of the distribution; β is the location parameter, which determines the horizontal position of the distribution.

Crack lengths for various fatigue cycle numbers, N , were measured from scanning electron micrographs and tabulated to obtain the experimental crack length distribution for each replica examined. Average crack length was calculated from the n individual crack lengths, L_i , according to:

$$\bar{L} = \sum L_i / n . \quad (5)$$

The standard deviation, σ , was calculated by the standard formula:

$$\sigma = (\sum (\bar{L} - L_i)^2) / n)^{\frac{1}{2}} . \quad (6)$$

The Weibull distribution shape parameter was estimated from the average length and standard deviation as follows (59):

$$\alpha = (\bar{L}/\sigma)^{1.06} \quad (7)$$

The Weibull distribution location parameter, β , which is the α th moment of the distribution, was then calculated as (54):

$$\beta = (\sum L_i^\alpha / n)^{1/\alpha} \quad (8)$$

Values of \bar{L} , σ , α , and β are given in Table II.

Table II. Values of Average Length, \bar{L} , Standard Deviation, σ , and Weibull Distribution Parameters for Fatigue Crack Initiation and Micro-crack Growth Experiments

Material	Stress Amplitude MPa	Number of Cycles	Weibull α	Weibull β	Average Length \bar{L}	Standard Deviation σ
Al 2124-T6	300	100	0.90	3.00	3.12	3.45
Heat #A8050W	300	500	1.07	4.21	4.10	3.85
	300	1500	0.58	6.72	9.66	16.10
Silag SiC (20 vol.% whisker)/Al (2124-T6)	300	4000	2.46	1.69	1.48	0.63
	300	7000	1.98	1.96	1.74	0.91
	300	10000	2.11	2.05	1.82	0.90
	300	13000	1.93	2.46	2.15	1.16
Heat #2038Z-C	300	16000	1.92	2.86	2.49	1.35
Silag SiC (20 vol.% whisker)/Al (2124-T6)	350	800	1.59	1.62	1.51	0.98
	350	2000	1.57	2.01	1.83	1.20
	350	4000	1.59	2.67	2.28	1.47
	350	5000	1.62	3.08	2.53	1.60
Heat #A2038Z-C						
Silag SiC (20 vol.% whisker)/Al (2124-T6)	300	100	1.79	1.84	1.65	0.95
	300	200	2.06	2.09	1.85	0.94
	300	300	1.59	2.12	1.93	1.29
	300	400	1.69	2.23	2.00	1.22
	300	500	1.65	2.48	2.10	1.31
Heat #A6104Z-2A	300	1000	2.03	4.23	3.52	1.81

Figure 14 shows the Weibull probability density function as a function of crack length for the three samples under study. Plots show the range from 1 micron, the smallest crack size measured, to the smallest value of the function greater than .01.

Figure 15 shows the crack lengths for which the value of the Weibull cumulative distribution function (Eq. 3) is 0.99 and 0.90, and the average crack length, \bar{L} , plotted as functions of number of cycles. The length for which the Weibull cumulative distribution function equals 0.99 marks the top 1% of the distribution (99th percentile); the length for 0.90 marks the top 10% (90th percentile). These measures illustrate the longest cracks which generally grow faster than the shorter ones and are thus more significant determinants of the likelihood of specimen failure. Figure 15A compares the two composite heats of the same volume fraction (SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/

Figure 14 - The Weibull probability density function as a function of crack length. A: Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4), Heat #A6104Z-2A, at 100, 500 and 1000 cycles, 300 MPa. B: Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Heat #A2038Z-C at 4000, 10000 and 16000 cycles, 300 MPa.

Figure 14 - The Weibull probability density function as a function of crack length. C: Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, at 800, 2000, and 5000 cycles, 350 MPa. D: Al (2124-T6), Heat #A8050W, at 100, 500 and 1500 cycles, 300 MPa.

Al (2124-T4), Heat #A6104Z-2A, Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, showing an improvement in fatigue crack resistance (i.e., the number of cycles required to reach a given average crack length) of more than an order of magnitude on going from the older to the newer composite. Figure 15B shows the effect of stress on the newer composite (Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C). Figure 15C compares the newer composite (Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C) to the unreinforced Al alloy 2124-T6 (Heat #A8050W) showing an advantage in crack resistance of two orders of magnitude for the composite.

The differences between the two batches of Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124) are: (a) the heat treatment, which perhaps accounts for a 7 percent improvement in yield strength on going from T4 to T6, based on the comparison given in (5), with allowances for the higher whisker volume fraction in the present case; (b) the reduction in number and size of non-SiC intermetallics on going from the older (SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4), Heat #A6104Z-2A) to the newer (SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2126-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C) material; (c) the reduction of clustering of SiC in the newer (SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C) material. The effect of yield strength should in this case be minor, as the tests are run at 300 and 350 MPa, while the cyclic yield strength for the newer Silag

Figure 15 - Crack lengths corresponding to 99% (dotted curves) and 90% (dashed curves) of the Weibull cumulative distribution function, and average crack length (solid curves with data points) as a function of number of cycles. A: Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4), Heat #A6104Z-2A, vs. Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, both at 300 MPa. B: Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, at 300 and 350 MPa.

Figure 15C - Crack lengths corresponding to 99% (dotted curves) and 90% (dashed curves) of the Weibull cumulative distribution function, and average crack length (solid curves with data points) as a function of number of cycles. Al (2124-T6), Heat #A8050W, vs. Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2126-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, both at 300 MPa.

SiC/Al is on the order of 580 MPa. The reduction of extrinsic defects is no doubt the major influence, since they are, in effect, already microcracks. There may be some difference in the strength of the whisker-matrix interface as well since the evolution of fatigue cracks is substantially retarded in the newer SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), (Heat #A2038Z-C).

The difference between the Silag SiC/Al (2124) and the unreinforced Al (2124-T6) is no doubt due to the reduction in yield strength due to the elimination of the SiC. At 300 MPa, the Al (2124-T6) is very close to its cyclic yield strength of 320 MPa, and should thus be much more susceptible to dislocation motion than the SiC/Al (2124) (yield strength of 580 MPa in the T6 condition for the newer Heat #A2038Z-C). The unreinforced Al (2124-T6) manifests slip band cracking, which is not observed in the SiC/Al (2124), and supports cracks up to 500 microns long as opposed to 30 microns in the SiC/Al

Figure 16 - Microcrack growth rate as a function of nominal stress intensity range for Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T6), Heat #A2038Z-C, and Silag SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4), Heat #A6104Z-2A at 300 MPa. Solid lines are individual cracks; dashed lines are average crack length. Crack lengths range from 1 to 12 microns.

Figure 17 - Microcrack growth rate as a function of nominal stress intensity range for Al(2124-T6), Heat #A8050W at 300 MPa. Crack lengths range from 1 to 123 microns.

(2124, both T4 and T6) at nominal stresses of 300 and 350 MPa. The inter-metallic particles in the unreinforced Al (2124-T6) are generally smaller than the SiC whiskers in the SiC/Al (2124), which should reduce the probability of fatigue crack initiation from the particles, in accordance with observations in 2024-T4 and 2124-T4 Al alloy by Kung and Fine (37). This is evidenced by the much lower density of cracks observed in the unreinforced Al (2124-T6) than in the SiC/Al (2124).

Crack Growth Rate

Growth rates of individual cracks were obtained by determining crack length change from one replica to the next and dividing by the number of cycles between replicas. The nominal stress intensity factor is calculated as:

$$\Delta K = \alpha/\sqrt{\pi L} . \quad (9)$$

Figure 16 shows crack growth rate as a function of nominal stress intensity range for the old and new Silag SiC/Al at 300 MPa. The variations in crack growth rate are associated with the location of the crack relative to the microstructure; growth is faster along the SiC-Al interface, slower through the Al matrix. This further shows that the interface is the weak link in the composite in the absence of extrinsic flaws. The longest crack thus far observed in the composite is 30 microns long; final failure typically occurs a few hundred cycles after this length is observed. This suggests a low fracture toughness which correlates with reported elongations to failure for this class of material of only a few percent (1).

Figure 17 shows fatigue crack growth rate as a function of nominal stress intensity range for Al (2124-T6), Heat #A8050W. The straight line is a least-squares fit to the data. Attempts at making similar plots for the composite showed too much scatter.

Comparison of Figs. 16 and 17 shows that the crack growth rate in the range $0.5 < \Delta K < 2.0$ is generally slower in the SiC (20 vol. pct. whisker)/Al (2124-T4 or T6) than in the Al (2124-T6) without SiC. The earlier discussion of deformation mechanisms and the scale on which they can operate can be applied to explain these results. The main effect is probably the reduction of slip distances in the SiC/Al-alloy due to the SiC. The development of slip bands ahead of the crack tip should accelerate crack growth by providing an easier path for the crack than exists without the slip bands. This slip band effect is apparently more significant than the relative brittleness of the SiC-Al interface, particularly since the Al (2124-T6) is much closer to its yield point than the SiC/Al (2124-T4 or T6).

Conclusions

The present work confirms earlier reports that the addition of SiC whiskers to aluminum alloy 2124 provides significant increases in elastic modulus, (cyclic) yield strength, and fatigue lifetime at the expense of ductility and fracture toughness. The interface between the SiC and Al acts as a crack nucleation site, and the link-up of microcracks must contribute to final fracture from a very short observed crack length (approximately 30 microns at an applied stress of 300 or 350 MPa). This lack of damage tolerance must place severe restrictions on the use of this material in fatigued structures since cracks this small cannot be observed by in situ non-destructive methods. Further research is needed to develop alloys and processes

which will provide better interfacial toughness. Some improvement may be possible by further reducing the size of the SiC reinforcement, following observations for other intermetallics in 2024-T4 and 2124-T4 Al alloy by Kung and Fine (38).

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